

EXPLORING THE CHALLENGES OF 4C'S ON 21ST CENTURY SKILLS OF EFL LEARNERS IN INDONESIA, MALAYSIA AND LIBYAN

Qurbonova Dilnoza Allanazarovna

National University of Uzbekistan, PhD student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10800391>

Abstract. The article explored the 4Cs notion, which refers to critical thinking, collaboration, and creativity as essential skills in the 21st century. The primary objective of this research is to explore how EFL classroom teachers in Indonesia, Malaysia, and Libya implement these four skills into their curricula. The research is inspired by the results and implementations of the abovementioned 4C skills.

Keywords: critical thinking, communication, collaboration, creativity.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada 21-asrda muhim ko'nikmalar sifatida tanqidiy fikrlash, jamoaviy ishlash va ijodkorlikni nazarda tutuvchi 4K tushunchasi o'rganildi. Ushbu tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi Indoneziya, Malayziya va Liviyadagi EFL sinf o'qituvchilari ushbu to'rtta ko'nikmalarni o'z o'quv dasturlariga qanday joriy qilishlarini o'rganishdir. Tadqiqot yuqorida aytib o'tilgan 4K ko'nikmalarining natijalari va amalga oshirilishidan ilhomlangan holda ilmiy kuzatishlarni olib borgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tanqidiy fikrlash, muloqot, jamoaviy ishlash, ijodkorlik.

Аннотация. В статье исследовалось понятие 4К, которое относится к критическому мышлению, сотрудничеству и творчеству как к важнейшим навыкам в 21 веке. Основная цель данного исследования — изучить, как преподаватели EFL в Индонезии, Малайзии и Ливии реализуют эти четыре навыка в своих учебных программах. Исследование основано на результатах и реализации вышеупомянутых навыков 4К.

Ключевые слова: критическое мышление, общение, сотрудничество, творчество.

Introduction

Significant changes have occurred in all facets of life in the 21st century, including education. Students in the 21st century should acquire different skills than those of the previous century. Educational institutions in today's world should also prepare students for a new social and economic environment as well as a more demanding and skill-focused job.

In 2002, the Partnership for 21st Century Skills, a collaboration between the U.S. Department of Education and several leading companies and organizations, introduced the concept of 4Cs. The goal was to address concerns that American education was not adequately preparing graduates for success in the Digital Economy. The 4Cs comprise four essential non-disciplinary core competencies: critical thinking and problem-solving, communication, collaboration, and creativity and innovation [2]. The 4C Skills are by far the most popular 21st Century skills. These skills are also called learning and innovation skills. These four skills are essential for modern students to succeed in school and the workplace. They often make the biggest impact in terms of setting your students apart when applying for and starting their careers. The term "4C" in the context of 21st-century skills typically refers to a set of skills deemed essential for success in the modern world. The 4Cs stand for:

Critical Thinking

Critical thinking is widely recognized as one of the essential skills needed in the 21st century due to the increasing complexity and rapid pace of change in today's world. It is the ability to analyze, evaluate, and synthesize information to make reasoned decisions and solve problems

effectively. Here are some reasons why critical thinking is important in the 21st century: In the digital age, we are bombarded with vast amounts of information from various sources. Critical thinking skills help individuals sift through this information, identify reliable sources, and discern fact from opinion or misinformation; In a fast-paced and constantly changing environment, individuals need to be able to think critically to assess situations, consider alternative solutions, and make informed decisions; In a rapidly changing world, individuals need to adapt and learn continuously and critical thinking skills provide a foundation for life-long learning by empowering individuals to ask questions, seek out new information, and critically evaluate their own beliefs and assumptions.

Developing critical thinking skills is crucial for individuals to thrive in the 21st century. Educators and employers increasingly emphasize the importance of critical thinking in education and the workplace, recognizing it as a key competency for success in a world that demands creative problem-solving, adaptability, and informed decision-making.

Communication

The skill of conveying ideas, thoughts, and information effectively through various means such as writing, speaking, and digital communication. In today's interconnected world, effective communication is crucial for collaboration, teamwork, and building relationships both in personal and professional settings. Communication is indeed a crucial learning skill that plays a significant role in various aspects of life, including education, professional development, and personal relationships.

Communication skills are essential for collaborative learning environments too. By effectively expressing ideas, actively listening to others, and providing constructive feedback, learners can work together more productively, share knowledge, and solve problems collectively. In essence, communication is not just a standalone skill but a foundational competency that underpins effective learning and success in all aspects of life. Therefore, investing in the development of communication skills is crucial for learners at all stages of their educational journey.

Collaboration

The capacity to work harmoniously with others towards a common goal, fostering teamwork, and utilizing the strengths of each team member. Collaboration is essential in many aspects of life, including the workplace, where diverse skills and perspectives often come together to achieve collective success. Collaboration is indeed a crucial 21st-century learning skill. Here are some reasons why collaboration is considered a vital skill for the 21st century: Many of the challenges we face today are multifaceted and require diverse perspectives and expertise to solve and collaborative efforts bring together individuals with different backgrounds, skills, and viewpoints, enabling more comprehensive problem-solving approaches; Collaboration fosters an environment where ideas can be freely shared and combined, leading to innovative solutions and creative outcomes; Brainstorming and exchanging ideas with others often spark new insights and possibilities that may not have been apparent when working alone.

Effective collaboration relies on clear communication, including active listening, articulating ideas, and providing constructive feedback. Collaborative projects provide opportunities for individuals to practice and develop these essential communication skills, which are valuable in both personal and professional contexts. These experiences help develop teamwork skills, as well as leadership qualities such as facilitating discussions, motivating others, and resolving conflicts.

Educational institutions and employers recognize the importance of collaboration as a 21st-century skill and often incorporate collaborative learning activities and group projects into their curriculum and training programs. By fostering collaboration, educators and organizations prepare individuals to thrive in a world where success often depends on the ability to work effectively with others toward common goals.

Creativity

The ability to think innovatively, generate new ideas, and approach challenges with an open mind. Creativity is increasingly recognized as a fundamental skill for success in the 21st century. In an era marked by rapid technological advancements, globalization, and complex problem-solving, creativity is not just a desirable trait; it's becoming essential for navigating the challenges and opportunities of the modern world. Creativity and critical thinking go hand in hand. Creative individuals are often adept at evaluating information, synthesizing diverse perspectives, and making informed decisions. They are not just passive consumers of knowledge but active participants in the learning process. Creativity fosters effective communication and collaboration skills. When individuals are encouraged to express their ideas creatively, they learn how to communicate their thoughts clearly and persuasively. Moreover, collaborative creativity encourages teamwork, empathy, and respect for others' perspectives. Engaging in creative activities allows individuals to express themselves, explore their interests, and cultivate a sense of purpose and joy. Creativity has the power to challenge norms, provoke thought, and inspire action. In an age of globalization and cultural exchange, creative expression catalyzes social change, fostering understanding, empathy, and unity across diverse communities.

In today's globalized world, 21st-century skills, such as communication, collaboration, creativity, and critical thinking are essential for successful EFL (English as a foreign language) learners in several countries. From the observation of Indonesia, Malaysia, and Libyan, acquiring these skills can be challenging due to the lack of experience and literate technology.

These countries have a beneficial long tradition of teaching English as a Foreign Language. The present study explores the challenges they face in adopting 21st-century learning skills such as 4C. The 21st-century skills are essential for preparing future generations to navigate rapid change, the global economy, and the use of computers. Therefore, teachers must master all the crucial requirements to face the challenges in teaching 21st-century skills, especially utilizing technology in classrooms, developing critical thinking between students and collaborative groups to improve students' understanding, and fostering self-directed learning. (Partnership for 21st Century Skills, 2010). To prepare students for the global economy, educators should prioritize acquiring 21st-century skills. Educational institutions should give students practical training to help them develop these abilities.

In this process, we can see an example of a Libyan secondary educational system that has a problem with implementing 21st-century skills. The schools lack language labs and audiovisual aids that can be used for language instruction, which makes it difficult for teachers to teach these skills. These resources are necessary for students to fully develop their communication and critical thinking skills. In addition to time constraints and large classes, these shortcomings exacerbate the challenges, causing teachers to make conscious decisions to teach specific skills and leave others out. Moreover, English teachers have no experience teaching 21st-century skills; they have not been appropriately trained for the job. They teach English for Libya's new curriculum without any prerequisites of teaching practice or special training in teaching 21st-century skills. [1]

Teachers in Indonesia experienced several problems in improving their student's 4C skills. One of them is that the teacher should be literate in technology. This necessity is an urgent thing to fulfill since technology roles facilitate students in achieving education in the 21st century such as communication skills, collaboration, creativity, innovation, independence, and so on. Modern educational thinkers have espoused different approaches to transform the 20th-century model of teaching and learning. Transformative systems enable the development of 21st-century competencies. They recognize that you can't effectively communicate, collaborate, innovate, or solve problems in the 21st century without technology (Malik, 2018). In addition, teachers encounter problems in their teaching practice in the twenty-first century, such as enhancing teaching quality, developing lesson plans, creating exercises based on learning objectives, customization, classroom management, content discussion, and mastery of learning tools. In other words, instructors in the 21st century face a problem in developing 4C abilities. Teachers continue to use traditional instructional methods and teacher-oriented strategies. Teachers have to find innovative and creative ways to present content to learners, including creativity in the use of media and suitable learning methods. Therefore, we have to assess the level of teacher readiness, including experience with ability literacy in technology, utilizing criteria that correlate with teachers' understanding of implementing 21st-century learning.

The Ministry of Education of Malaysia has introduced a 21st Century Learning, or Pembelajaran Abad ke-21 (PAK21) to prepare youth for this 21st century. It has initially transformed Malaysia's education system for teachers and students to experience more creative thinking processes and encourage better human values. Therefore, PAK21 has offered three major skills, which are life and career skills, learning and innovation skills, and information, media, and technology skills. The achievement of PAK21 requires teachers' commitment to preparing students to master subject content, communication, collaboration, critical thinking, creativity, and technology literacy. [4]

In Indonesia, four English teachers from different Junior High Schools in Garut (two teachers from a private school and two teachers from a public school) were involved in this research. This is due to the assumption that there are differences in the challenges of teaching English in private and public schools; such as the students' learning resources, the school infrastructure, teaching techniques, and teaching the media.

For Libyan countries, this study focuses on the implementation of 21st-century skills at 1st-year secondary state schools and the teachers' challenges in doing so. It covers twenty schools in Tripoli that are considered typical or representative of Libyan secondary state schools.

And in Malaysia a total of 57 teachers from different states of Malaysian secondary school participated in this survey.

In this study, the survey research method was chosen for multi-country experiences as it was the most systematic and comprehensive way to obtain the personal opinions and perceptions of people. Quantitative data were collected to elicit responses to the research questions along with semi-structured interviews were used as research tools.

From the discussion, the findings indicate that Malaysian secondary school teachers are aware of the importance of technology in 21st-century learning, but they have less confidence in using technology in daily teaching. This may be due to less training and exposure to the technology. The findings also indicate that teachers need professional development to enhance their teaching. Ongoing professional development is critical for teachers who wish to be great at their jobs and offer the best to their students. Professional development not only allows teachers

to learn new teaching styles, techniques, and skills but also interact with educators from other areas to improve their teaching.

EFL teachers in Indonesia faced various challenges in developing students' 4C skills in 21st-century education. This point discusses the challenges teachers face as seen from 4C points, namely critical thinking skills, creativity skills, communication skills, and collaboration skills. Teachers are influential and significant agents for change and development in Libya. They coordinate critical activities to manage the country's educational system effectively. This study shows why mastering 21st-century skills is vital for teachers, especially in a fast-changing world associated with rapid technological and economic development. In the knowledge economy, this set of skills has a place. Employers seek employees who can "think outside the box" or show collaboration, creativity, and self-direction.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the data analysis, it can be concluded that both Indonesian EFL teachers of public and private schools in junior high school had similar problems in developing students' 4C skills in 21st-century education (critical thinking, creativity, communication, and collaboration). The challenges faced by teachers include the difficulties in understanding certain effective methods of learning that support the development of 4C skills, the obstacles in designing a lesson plan for 4C skills, the limited infrastructure, and the students' condition who lacked confidence, activeness, and ability to express their opinion. In addition, the teachers believed that 4C skills were hard to implement because of the condition of the students who were mostly mid to low in terms of capacity in English skills. Hence, the teachers claimed that the basic competence of students in English was still not adequate and it became a challenge for them to develop 4C skills in 21st-century education [5].

The difficulties Libyan teachers mentioned mainly were that students face difficulties with reading. Some students can hardly express themselves clearly in English. Teachers claim that students do not possess strong English language skills. Nevertheless, they agree that the 21st-century skills curriculum fosters more excellent linguistic skills and delivers the intended outcomes. Teachers agree that 21st-century skills are essential for their students' future success. However, most participants said that the most significant difficulties involved implementation due to a lack of suitable materials and resources. In other words, they complain about the lack of teaching materials and that students are not developing and improving in language as they should be. Thus, it is not shown that 21st-century skills are effective. The skills are either age-inappropriate, ineffective, or misunderstood [1].

On average, Malaysian teachers know teaching and learning deliveries but still lack 21st-century knowledge, understanding, and skills. The lack of this 21st-century knowledge, understanding, and skills would restrain teachers from diverging their modesty in teaching deliveries. There is still a lot of work and research that could be done to study in infusing 21st-century learning skills to students. But still, teachers need to be refined first as they are the agents of change in 21st-century learning. The proper module on implementing and assessing the PAK21 should be provided to teachers and an appropriate schedule and practicum should be conducted to improve teacher's skills and fulfil 21st-century students' needs.

Teachers are in charge of the successful implementation of 21st-century learning. Teachers' perspectives, knowledge, abilities, and performance all have an impact on their students' learning outcomes. Teaching in the 21st century is challenging, and instructors must focus on the 4 Cs of learning: creativity, collaboration, and critical thinking. Teachers should be allowed to advance

their profession because they are convinced that professional development would assist them improve their knowledge and increase their capacity in teaching and assessing. Teachers require materials and references to assist them in teaching. Teachers desire guidelines that will encourage their creativity in developing effective, relevant, and enjoyable teaching strategies. Teachers cannot act alone in delivering successful 21st-century learning. One of the most effective methods to help teachers is to provide a teaching module that includes activities relevant to 21st-century learning abilities. The curriculum is practical, and teachers may instantly implement the proposed exercises. Furthermore, teachers can include or change the suggested activities into new activities to make them more meaningful in their instruction.

REFERENCES

1. Aya Edawi Wheida. Implementing English for Libya 21st century Skills in First-Year State Secondary Schools, University of Tripoli, 2023
2. Charles Kivunja. Exploring the Pedagogical Meaning and Implications of the 4Cs “Super Skills” for the 21st Century through Bruner’s 5E Lenses of Knowledge Construction to Improve Pedagogies of the New Learning Paradigm School of Education, The University of New England Creative Education, 2015, №6, P. 224-239.
3. Halah Ahmed Alismail Dr. Patrick McGuire. 21st Century Standards and Curriculum: Current Research and Practice, Department Curriculum and Instruction, School of Education, University of Colorado Colorado Springs, 1420 Austin Bluffs Pkwy, Colorado Springs, CO 80918, Journal of Education and Practice ISSN 2222-1735 (Paper) ISSN 2222-288X (Online) Vol.6, No.6, 2015
4. Nor Hazizah Julaihi & Aniza Hamdan. Malaysian secondary school teachers’ readiness in implementing 21st century learning (PAK21), Universiti Teknologi MARA, Samarahan Campus, 94300 Kota Samarahan, Sarawak. 2019 1st International Conference on Education in the Digital Ecosystem (ICEdDE 2019)
5. Siti Nur Azizah Septiyanti; Yustika Nur Fajriah. The challenges encountered by EFL teachers in developing students’ 4C skills in 21st-century education, Institut Pendidikan Indonesia Garutt, Journal of English Pedagogy and Applied Linguistics Vol. 1, No. 2, Tahun 2021 <https://ejournal.masoemiversity.ac.id/jepal/index.php/englishpedagogy>,
6. Sunardi., & Doringin, F. (2020). The 4Cs learning model in teacher professional development program. *Humaniora*, 11(2), 153-159. <https://doi.org/10.21512/humaniora.v11i2.6508>
7. <http://www.21stcenturyskills.org>